

Roman Science Inspired by Emerging JWST Results: [website](#), [proceedings](#), [video](#)

Session 1 live-captioning, Tuesday 20 June 2023:

[Roman Space Telescope mission overview and community engagement, plus a Juneteenth celebration](#)

Nancy Levenson: Welcome to STScI

I thought I'd mention a couple of three things about our role here. So with Roman Science, we had the operation center, but that's very much something that we do in partnership with the project especially at Goddard, and also with our partners at iPad. This is very much a combined effort in bringing together our strength and abilities to be able to support this mission. But here at STScI, we are responsible for the science mission operations. And if you cross and multimission things and in particular for space telescope. Which gathers the data not only for those major missions that we support, but also over 20 additional missions. For those of you organizing your own mission, we welcome your data and we hope you could talk to us about that. Something else that is very crosscutting at the Institute, is public outreach. So you should be able to share the excitement of the science that businesses represent. The signs that you exist dominoes are doing, but you'll be able to share that with the world. So that is something that is also really rewarding. So, overall, a lot of what the Institute does, we support the science income and enable you science. So that is very much the reason that we are here. I know that coming up in this conference will be hearing a bit more about the mission, and some of the hardware and progress. In the short answer is there's great progress and were looking forward to the launch that will be here before we know it. So things are in good shape. So what that means is that for those of us interested in the science outcome, that we have a great opportunity. We have great opportunities over a full range -- We have someone who is not muted or seems like were getting some feedback. All right -- I was talking about our great science opportunities that we have available in these different fields. They are the core community surveys, but they themselves are broad, and they have to dual a lot with making those full surveys for all of astrophysics. And of course from the core community surveys and independent work, all of the data will be public which means there are multiple opportunities for reuse, and investigations in different directions. Some of what the mission represents is new ways of working. In new ways for us with large volumes of data, is being able to do data-driven astronomy and also having the opportunity of using science platforms which for some people, myself included, is something new. But I'm also really excited about that opportunity because it

also represents the possibility for greater accessibility and inclusion. That these data do not depend on what kind of organization you are part of overall kindness resources you might have direct access. But really you should be able to get the best science out of the overall. And of course, it is not an isolation, we have many other exciting things for ourselves as astronomers coming online, eminently soon roommate and in the near-term future, some of the 30-meter telescopes on the ground will also have great opportunities. As well as the existing space facility in Graham facilities that we have access to. So again, there are ways to use the observation of the data in combination for greater results. So bottom line, I'm really glad that you're all here and I'm glad J.J. able to share what you are doing to share your own areas of resource with creatures with us, and I encourage you to be engaged in this exciting mission so we can generate the greatest result out of it. So thank you all very much, and the meat not pass it back to you Dominique. Disappeared without a chance for questions, but I don't know if we have any questions out here online -- also seems that we do have a question. We have a runner.

I am a freelance writer -- and I wanted to ask if this is your first space science mission with Roman Science? And if so, either way, this is kind of a funny comment, but I don't know if people will know that because we say last name in Roman is the last name -- I don't know if we could ever or perhaps change the tone quality in Nancy Roman? It gets the idea or the concept out there. That was my comment/question. So I realize I don't know enough of the history. I'm not aware of dangerous space missions. It especially the first astrophysics mission, and speaking as Nancy Levenson I am all in favor. I'm glad that you notice that because it is implied intentional. And some of you may remember when I had a list of my office while on the people of their unk under consideration. In the list was chosen for people who had significant contribution to space astrophysics and who had not been recognized 90 space missions. Not surprisingly many of them were women. I think there's something to that. That was one of the names on our list. Yes, and are not so particularly great one and what I see is a lot of opportunity for interaction and the scientific synergy as Nancy Grace yes.

Julie McEney: Roman Science and Mission Updates

I am now going to introduce the senior project scientists and a person you should all be looking to to first of all informing about the mission and its status on what is going to happen but also making sure that impact does happen. Of course she is mostly known as a game away astronomy and now she's the infrared astronomy. To her next project is going to be a space-based radio telescope. Julie McEney. So all the word about my size coming up -- I'll get started. Though it is really a pleasure to be here. I became the project scientists the senior project scientists during the pandemic. So, the Saints team has founded also within the pandemic. So this is the first time that I've had the opportunity to attend a Roman science conference in person. And will rise on the threshold of selecting a new set of funding or a new set of teams in the community that I hope I will have the opportunity to be in person at the senior project. So, I wanted to start -- actually the questions was very well poised. Because I really wanted to start with why we are called the Nancy space Roman space telescope. It was the fish she was the first chief astronomer. And she sometimes as the mother of space, because I know she made that space mission come to pass but that doesn't really give her full justice because

she was really a person who had the vision and the drive to make space-based astronomy the thing at NASA. So, when it comes to naming, so similar to how they ask the people to refer to the observatory as the room's observatory so you do not lose their name. Similarly with Roman, we prefer that people call it the Nancy Grace Roman observatory -- or the Roman space telescope, because we do know her name to get lost in an acronym. And for sure, Roman is much easier to say than MGR FT. Which you occasionally see happen. So it answers the question, I hear your point that when you just use somebody's silly name, there's an assumption that the person is a male, and I architected assumption we should push back on in general. So hopefully this observatory being named after Nancy Grace Roman is one step in that direction. Okay so what is the realm and mission objective? So this is the statement of what we are here for and what we are doing. But, it is worth studying here because this is what drives the mission design being what it is. In jives and what it means to think about observation. So in the very first missive objection if read the document looks for all the astrophysics that you can do wide area surveys. And that astrophysics is from an extremely broad and varies. There is a requirement that gets attached to it that we should have imaging of at least a certain magnitude of at least 20 square degrees. I'm really emphasizing this because the same survey, and we will address in the next two mission objectives is also this astrophysics objective. And what I want you to really understand is that astrophysics is not secondary involvement and insignificant secondary Roman and that the core community service were always intended to address cosmology and astrophysics is one the three pillars of which Roman stands. The second mission objective here extension history of the universe and growth and structure of the universe combined. The two of them will give you a picture of dark energy and dark matter and the evolution within the universe. And the goal here is to study each of these with multiple techniques. To batten down uncertainties. And we have a mission objective to form a sense of extra planet from the outer habitable zone. And that is code for use the microlensing technique to open up the window in the equivalent outer solar system and beyond. I know that this does not mean that we cannot find met very many planets via the transit techniques. Documented in recent paper. We are not locking up entire observing program into the large surveys that will support the first four goals, we also have an allocation that would call general surgery, and this is for all the signs that you can do with Roman, that cannot be achieved with the survey that we will also used to cosmology in the demographic. So this could include things like survey of the Milky Way or nearby galaxies. Finally, Roman will also conduct cartographic technology demonstration. We have two instruments, the first one addresses the top size objective in the sixth objectives is a technology demonstration to demonstrate advance in space. Okay so the observatory instrument Roman has -- I'm speaking to people who know when we to say here but I will say this anyway, we have a 2.4-meter aperture. So we have a sensitivity and a performance that is a privilege to a couple and we have two instruments the welfare instruments which looks at infrared -- it has a filter view 5.4 degrees and it is instrumented with 18 by four by 4K Play for Kay detectors. The instrument is indivisible, and is designed to provide a contrast of 10¹⁰ minus nine or little bit more about that later. I haven't described this yet in detail, but Roman has a filter view that is over a hundred times larger than Hartl -- but ovulation is that we are designed to look at it efficiently silly or deserved it more than a thousand times faster so we have very large state of volume. Which translates into a infant interesting transformation on the golf people like you who was of the analysis over the two. And that is the same orbit as a Steve. This orbit

allows us for a very stable operations which contribute to the ability of Roman that sees what possible bubble and that is important for our site. It also means that it's definitely in the field of view. We are currently working on a 2026 launch. every committed to a lunch before May 2027. So you will occasionally hear both of those dates. Our mission duration is five years with a 10-year goal, and a much longer time frame. If you're interested in the detailed performance of Roman, please go to the page at the bottom of the screen the link, I will provide information on the several times around the sensitivity and performance of our instruments. I'm going to march through these next two slides quickly. So it has filters the instrument, one wideband filter that will make a quick measurement of brightness of something. In seven Darryl Brown filters that fully cover the available range provided by the rim protectors and the mirrors. In 2020, we added the readiness filter there, when it became available. We also have a way to provide -- so here you see the effective areas of the prism in the chrim and the wideband filters. The person tells a little bluer than the chrim and has a higher enterprise of lower resolution. So what you use depends on your science case so, I want to come back into on this just a little bit. The power of rural Maine isn't just that we have a large you'll which is very nice but we have efficient observations. We can settle quickly and be ready to take the next image. That opens up signs cases for people who want to do a large number of sort observations to map out regions of the sky, or for rapid time domain observations. Because we are at this second stage, we don't have certain anomalies, so when I say that we surveyed the sky a thousand times faster, what that means is that our main survey which will take something like around two years with Roman, will take over 2,000 years with the other program. So what we do it's not faster, we as a capability of probing new scientific space, space space, and doing some thing that is unachievable with this program, because we have this program in the direction of a larger field of view. It is important to the improvement of the FT over the other program, which has sensitivity and it goes further to the infrared section. Assessment aspect of Roman that is important is our mission objective and cosmology is the drive requirements for high precision stability. So we have a very well understood function which is necessary to measure food we cleansing which is one of our key mission objective team performance allows you to measure the shape of anything else. He kisses very Kurdish geometry for the sets of science case studies opened up by that. We have excellent calibration through onboard -- I realize I forgotten -- through onboard calibration system again this is driven by a mission objectives. Weather radio the be hugely little useful for a broad range of signs case. So, what we've been discussing so far has been focusing on the Whitefield instrument, and that will be the case through most of this talk, but I do not want to lose sight of the fact that we have a coronagraph on Brian that in its own way will be spectacular a coronagraph is a little bit like magic with physics will you take advantage of the wave properties to create destructive interference at the spot of your style that you are observing. So that you zero it out. And allow the possibility of imaging nearby. At the planets around that start. With the coronagraph, we will be demonstrating the use of deformable mirrors in space and we will be demonstrating the use of sensing and control. And we will be demonstrating the power for ground algorithms to pull out features surrounding of the nearby stars. Okay, so here's a picture of a Roman observatory hardware, I realized that you have already seen something similar to this I wanted to show to you all again. Just to put it into context some of the pictures that I am going to show you next. So, if I have to summarize what I'm trying to say in this talk, is that Roman is an awesome mission is going to do great science. Enrollment is well on its way to

being built, and our flight hardware, most of our flight hardware is in hand in were in the midst of integration or we are past our peak funding year. On the third point I wanted to make is that now is the time to really get engage on shaping what we actually do at this observatory. So starting with -- already covered that were going to do great science a limited talk now a little bit about where we are with hardware status. So if you look at the bottom of this central image, you can see on October shape that is -- a hexagon that is our spacecraft structure. In this structure is here. He lives in the clean room. In each of those have the door, and the hardware is mounted on the door so he can close the door from everything being ready, because it's mounted on the door, the dash the Heat generate gymnast a simulated the outside. The resident of South Korea was off the window while we were doing this move that is a complete coincidence. But we were actually planning to do the move that they would just shift at the time a little bit so that the timing would work out. But the real point I want you to get from this and everything that I'm going to show, is that Roman is really real. We are building this and is incredibly exciting. Okay, so here's a few more pictures of the spacecraft. So this is a -- on the top left -- and are critical to everyone of these pictures, seek and relax is gonna be okay. But I doing to talk about some of them. So we built a mock version of the spacecraft to run the flight harnesses, and then use that to do more of to provide that -- or that is 44 miles of harness weighing over a thousand pounds. So just the cables are Roman has the same mass as many people and other missions. Across this spacecraft, everything else is being worked on in parallel. So we're working on the project and the content knows, and on the sooner panels. It is all OCO. And here's a photograph that was done just outside the clean room and if you want to know the answer, yes they fit so that was good. Moving onto the Whitefield instrument. Here are also where things are going great. The focal plane away array, was completed, and we replace three detectors in the array because they had a change in performance between one of the tests and the terminal backtest. And we now believe that we understand the origin of the change. And our confidence -- and we will continue to have a focal plane that is significantly exceeding requirements. The focal plane system itself is the Eric Shawn express the focal plane array have been put together. They've been shipped out to airspace, and it is of course the beating heart of the instrument right. That is where -- first the photons will get protected. They've been shipped in Colorado, where they have been installed into the cold -- and sensing module also installed is the elephant will the assembly. So the wheel that contains the filter we've delivered the source which is a piece of test equipment. So the bottom line is that the instrument is really coming along and looking very much like an instrument. At this point, we are now pretty far down the track of having really nice text data of our flight detectors and associated electronics and it's really great to see some such a great performing instrument. So the coronagraph instrument, is also going great. All the flight hardware is at JPL, there is an excellent margin against requirements which is good, because there chronograph is really there is a hole that you want to push the bounds on the instrument to get the best not just for a technology demonstration, but to do even more as possible. So, here you have got a picture of the fully populated object, and it's really quite -- the thing that you see little drawings off really exists. So telescope here, before the structure assembly that is the primary mirror, and a secondary mirror with the Association instructor, and is being put together and it's complete and we are now working on the other optics. So, now I would like to transition into what we're going to do with Roman, and Reagan are here much more about this from -- but how we make observations is an intrinsic part of this mission. So first a quick comment on the

nature -- if you use wide-field survey or point source, it will equal the performance. If you use wide-field survey to study something that completely fills the point of view, you will have over a hundred times in performance. If you use it to survey the sky you will have more than a thousand times of the performance. In the point I really want to make is that in your mind you should be thinking about Roman and surveys because that is what we do really well. And that doesn't mean that it's a bad thing to take Roman and go on point out of particular spot right -- we should always pursue the best science, but in your mind, we really want people to be thinking to the degree possible in how we can make best use of this great point of view and how can we make disability to -- that is what we call all Roman observation of a survey. Because even if you only care about the single-point source, to doing a survey because the whole rest of the field is still there. And our observations, they are split. We have three core community surveys. That addresses the 2010 the Cato survey science goals. So those are broadly the objects is that I showed you at the beginning of this presentation. These surveys are high latitude wide area surveys. In this video survey with spectroscopy. It enables the weak lensing and the cosmology mission objectives and it is also assumed to be the survey that will address our need for wide area surveys for infrared -- the high latitude wide survey is the survey that will take over 2,000 years with them better look openly in large regions and getting us out that lampposts and the time domain will explore this guy and a new area safe space in the time domain. So here's what we'll be doing and we were going to the same tens of degrees patch of the sky every five days or so and we will look at everything this change. Due to be outstanding for finding a detecting and characterizing supernova but also find destruction event in GammaRay afterglow sink in the nova and find things that we do not currently know about, because that always happened. And they have a way to explore the sky. The final server instead of looking away from our collective planes is looking towards the center of our galaxy, and in this case what we're doing is looking out a couple of square degrees towards the center of the galaxy towards the galactic bulge, an empty 15 minutes were cycling around. In this enables microlensing this in objectives but of course if you're monitoring carefully the brightness is 700 million stars going to enable a lot of astrophysics. If you have an incredibly deep observation in the near infrared close to the galactic center, you're enabling so population astrophysics. So the science out of each of these surveys will be incredibly rich and incredibly broad in unachievable until -- without Roman. We have at least 25 time generated -- and it is a way to respond to the wing changing their right scientific landscapes and to address things that be done with one of the three core community surveys. And then of course there's the technology demonstration. I'm going to get a little bit of over the long because my time is ticking. So, I wanted to say a little bit about a field of regard, but we have got to stay at least 54 degrees away from it. And do equivalent from this direction that means that the entire middle focus is completely available. And as I've mentioned what its width it is emphasized in our school and settle and rapid steps essential for being able to conduct or quickly map across the sky. In the expectation is that the main survey is going to be a -- within 20 degrees of proposed so that's keeping within the continuous viewing zones so that you can have continuous observations across several years, it is not possible to have continuous observations at the galactic center so here the galactic bulge is visible for the year. As you will hear later, we have not decided exactly what each of the core community surveys will be. However, we have time fairly detailed definitions of what we call a design reference mission. And this allows to verify that you really can meet our science objectives within the

lifetime of the mission. So each of these three defined surveys in the design reference Mission represents a use space. It gives you a flavor for what the actual surveys might look like. So what you are seeing here in equatorial coordinates is the high latitude wide area survey in red, the high latitude time domain survey in blue. You see the two little spots there. And then, finally, you can hardly see it -- the little baby pink dot is the galactic bulge time domain survey. No less important for covering a smaller region of the sky, because what it loses in sky coverage, it more than makes up for in exploration in the time domain. We are in the middle of the process of engaging with the community to decide, where do we want the footprint of the surveys to be? What filters do we want to use? What cadence? And what I really want to emphasize is that there is considerable flexibility, and there is considerable flexibility because, by design, the design reference mission did not have margin. We had margin between predicted performance and the science requirements, in the sense that each of those three had more than address the cosmology and exoplanet demographic requirements. There was explicit margin. We did not assign every single day there is in those five years, because the purpose was to show that the surveys fit. And then, finally, there is implicit margin, and the implicit margin, I think, is important. For example, in the design reference mission, it was assuming a slew rate, assuming we are using five reaction wheels. But we actually have six reaction wheels, so in reality, we will be able to slough and settle faster, and add to the field in that amount of time. We were assuming that the detectors were at 95% comparability, which is the requirement, but we are seeing much more performance from our detectors. So you can assume additional implicit margin there. The reason I'm mentioning this is that, in the process of defining the core community surveys, we are not just exploring if there is another way to construct to the community survey that addresses the cosmology or exoplanet requirements while also doing astrophysics. There is more for you to play with here. So there really is opportunity to either enhance the core community surveys to do even broader astrophysics return, or to make a decision that that time is better used in the general astrophysics survey part for whatever arises. I'm really looking forward to seeing how the community gets together to make recommendations on those things. So the core community surveys are for everyone, every single room and observation will be used by multiple people, so we need a cooperative process for deciding how to define the operations. We need everybody's ideas to be considered. Please join in. The general astrophysics surveys, at least 25% of the time is devoted to general astrophysics surveys. We did realize that there was a possibility that we are leaving science on the table by waiting until just before launch to define the general astrophysics survey, so we asked for white papers to make the case for defining one of the general astrophysics surveys now. Things that would benefit from early definition surveys, and we got a set of white papers. Let me just move on. I'm kind of running out of time, and these are the slides I was expecting to see here. I'm fine on time? Okay. Okay, so, then I will dwell a little bit on this, because I think it's actually kind of cool. So we recognized that we might be leaving science on the table by waiting until just before launch to define all the general astrophysics surveys, that there might be cases where you really would benefit by taking precursor observations of the field knowing where it actually is, or you can coordinate a community better. So what we suggested is, let's consider one month and observations to be executed sometime in the first two years. So this is not early science. It is not something that will be executed early. It is early definition. And what we wanted was a substantive survey. Something is not going to commit to a large amount of early observation time that is likely that we are going to want to

decide closer to launch. At least most of the general astrophysics survey time to be signed closer to launch. The expectation is that, if we proceed with this, the remaining general astrophysics survey time would be assigned via a traditional proposal process, or possible additional process closer to her after lunch. So, this was a two-step process. The first step was to request white papers. These were received. We then had a fairly long hiatus while you're waiting for the survey report to come out, and then complete a review for astronomy and astrophysics to decide broader questions and better observing programs. That's not complete. We are in the middle of evaluating those white papers and you can expect a resolution sometime in the next month or so. If the community, which is currently beating the recommended proceeding, we will have a community process to define whatever this new survey is, and it'll become a fourth -- it won't be a core community survey, but it will be a community survey defined the same way. Okay, so I'm almost at the end of my time. [Laughs] Kari is going to discuss community engagement in more detail, but saying multiple times, it is exceptionally important to us, the community engagement and defining what we are going to do with this mission, how we're going to work together on this mission, in all aspects. Not just what the observations are going to be, but what we're going to run in our pipelines, how we want to work together. So we have put some thought into your options for engaging. So you will hear a lot about how you can help and define the core community surveys. There are also options to directly engage with us on technical matters, like calibration software. We plan to add additional groups like astrometry. These are simple to join, there's a web sign-up page. It's a rolling deadline. We also plan to set up community-led science collaborations. We will probably start with cosmology exoplanet astrophysics. These are intended to be forums for people with similar interests, where they can come together and engage with one another. It also provides an option for advocacy in those science areas to make their way to the science centers. And finally there is funding, and funding is important. Many of you may have submitted a proposal to the recent ROSES called. The review of those proposals has happened, a decision has been made, and we are working through the final details to get ready to make an announcement. So it really is imminent. If you didn't propose, or you were not successful, they will be another call into coyyears' time. I haven't talked about science in a huge amount of detail, because that's the whole purpose of this conference, but I want to emphasize again that the Roman science many is exceptionally broad, with both the core community surveys and the general astrophysics surveys. My final point is that we are more than halfway through the process. We are past the peak funding year. We have our flight hardware in hand. We are just about to set up science collaborations. We are in the process of working with the community on the survey definition. I am hoping that it just gets better from here, and that the science centers and the project and the community start working closer and closer together with an end result of fabulous science in a few years from now, and I think it's going to be an exciting ride.

Thank you. We have time for questions. Unfortunately for the people online, there has been a problem with -- I believe, with the display, so we are resetting that right now. I apologize if this may flicker in other magical things. Either by blue jeans or the Slack channel, and I think we have our first question from blue jeans. Yes, can people propose cadence operation? Yes. The answer was yes. [Laughs] I mean, I can expand a little bit. The question is, can you propose cadence observations? And for a mission that so naturally has applications, I think it is important

to be able to accept those kinds of proposals. I think we need to think through the details of exactly how to get the right balance of enabling, over-mortgaging the future we don't want to end up in a situation where we have observing time for later years of proposals. Are there any questions in the room? Thanks very much. I see on this timeline here that there is a 5-year permission there's a chance that Roman will live past that mission, and I'm curious, does any of that get taken into account when selecting or defining the core community surveys? The quick answer is, not directly, in the sense that we are not going to try and schedule anything beyond the end of the prime mission. To demonstrate that we have met our mission objectives, we have to demonstrate that we met them within the prime mission. However, when the Coronagraph, for example, finishes its technology demonstration observations after 18 months, there may be a push to continue observations with the Coronagraph. And doing that will require re-planning everything else beyond the first five years. We might see some flexibility. The question you didn't answer, as we go through the prime phase of the mission, at some point we are going to want to come together as a community and think about, what do we want to do with the next five years? I think that could be anything from going to a fully proposal-driven direction, or there may be other large ambitious community surveys that become obvious after the first five years of observation. So I would kind of like everybody to be thinking, how might we use the second five years of operations, so when the time comes, we can make these choices? If there are no further questions, let's think Julie again.

Karoline Gilbert: Engaging with Roman

Now we have Karoline Gilbert, she will tell us about engaging with Roman on what Julie just said. Karoline has been here as a mission scientist for Roman and has been instrumental in leading the developed of the science operations here. Please tell us how we engage. I'd be happy to. All right. How's that, Thomas? Good? [Inaudible] Are be online okay? I think that's a thumbs up. Is it not on? Ah, better. Yes. Always a good first step. All right. Thanks, everyone. Thank you, Julie, for an excellent introduction to Roman and how exciting it's going to be for generally almost everyone. I am now actually the project scientist as of a few weeks ago, as my focus has turned more towards the sorts of things I'm going to talk to you about today. Namely, engaging the community with Roman and preparing to use this incredible survey facility. I'm going to spend most of my time talking today about how we are planning to define the community surveys for Roman, and most importantly, how you can get involved in doing so. Julie touched on the other ways of the end of her presentation, for you to engage Roman. This gives you kind of a timeline view of how you can get engaged in Roman. And I will go through them again towards the end, so you will get to see this again. First, starting by defining these incredible core community surveys. Just to reorient ourselves, we are talking about these three high latitude wide area survey, high latitude time domain survey, and the galactic bulge time domain survey, but while they will be the majority of the reserving time, there's also the general astrophysics surveys that Julie talked about. But what I wanted to stress here is that all of these observations, everything that Roman takes, is going to be public immediately. That data will hit the archive and anyone can access it. So this means that we really do anticipate that the main component of how the community engages with Roman is going to be Roman's data and Roman's archive. So since the core community surveys are the majority of the observing time,

that means, to have the greatest impact on the community that engages with Roman, we really need to make those as broadly applicable to the community as possible. As a going through this talk and talking about how we are going to define surveys, I want you to be considering whether you should be contributing to this. And just to kind of prime the wheels a little bit. This is just talking about three potential examples out of a lot of different things for the surveys, but the high latitude wide area survey, if you were interested in studying how galaxies change over time, how galaxy morphology changes with redshift, how interactions between galaxies change over redshift, anything like that, we are looking at, of order, 2,000 square degrees of the sky imaged in multiple bands to deep depths with Hubble-like resolution. This is going to be incredible. Of course, how incredible it is for your specific science might depend a lot on the specifics of what filters are chosen, for example. The high latitude time domain survey. Yes, it's going to discover and characterize a wonderful wealth of type 1A supernovae, but as Julie mentioned, there's an entire universe of rare transient objects out there that it will also discover characterize. Whether you are rare transient of choice is how well you can do that, it might also depend on, say, the cadence that is chosen, and the filters, again. And the galactic bulge time domain survey is going to meet the exoplanet objectives of the mission. It's also going to be an incredible survey if you are interested in studying stellar astrophysics. Again, just how incredible is probably going to depend on the details of how it's implemented. The goal for defining the core community surveys is truly to maximize the overall science return from these wide-field surveys. Of course we do need to do that while meeting the mission requirements that are focused on cosmology and exoplanets. And Julie discussed the design reference mission, and these survey strategies were incredibly useful and incredibly powerful to show that Roman, as designed, can meet its requirements as a mission. But the actual surveys that will be implemented are not set yet. They will be defined by this community process. So how are we going to do that? We are planning on standing up very soon a series of committees. There will be one survey definition committee for each survey, and then there will also be a Roman observations time allocation committee. So I'll go into a little bit more detail about what the definition committees will do in a second. Basically, as it sounds, they are going to be responsible for actually figuring out how we should define the surveys to get the broadest possible science out of them. They will come up with options, like a nominal implementation as well as options for enhanced scopes that will go into the room, and it'll be the enviable task of that committee to decide based on what they have received and provide recommendations on what the balance of observing time between these three core community surveys should be in with the total amount of time allocated to them should be based on the input they receive from the definition committees. What I want to stress is that these committees are going to be your committees. They are going to be charged with understanding and representing the entire breadth of science the astronomy community wants to see done at Roman's core community surveys. This means there are no survey teams being selected either to define surveys or implement the surveys. The surveys will be defined for this community process and he will be implemented by science centers. So, the timeline. This is where things get exciting. We are planning towards an October 2026 launch. We need to get the surveys defined so that, when you get your call for proposals, a year before launch, and you're trying to decide what you want to propose to observe with Roman, to do the science you are interested in doing, or what you want to propose in terms of the data analysis program to, say, analyze data from the core community surveys, you need to understand what these surveys can do,

what they are going to be. That is part of what drives this timeline. So there's a few stages. We have just finished our initial request for community input. We asked this winter for people to submit short science pitch is about the science they were excited to do with the core community surveys, and this past Friday we requested white papers to go into more detail about the science that people wanted to do with Roman's core community surveys and how the communities should -- what would be needed to do that science, what observational strategies like filters, cadence, depth, were important for their science, and how the communities could figure out, when they are considering those things, how it would impact their science. So that was the first stage. We received a really great response to both of these requests for input, so we got over 100 science pitches. They covered a really broad range of science topics. This was true for all three surveys. So this shows on the left, the scientific categories we ask people to tell us what their observations fit into what categories. And then, on the right is a word cloud of the optional keywords that it could provide to us. And you've got all these categories represented, and exoplanets, galaxies, stars, they are all about equally represented in the science that people want to do with the surveys. You can get a lot more detail he check out the newsletter article that summarizes the science mission. We haven't had much time to dig into the white papers yet, since they were due Friday. But I can tell you we had a great response. We got 71 unique white papers. A few of them discuss topics they said applied to more than one survey. The numbers here at up to more than 71. We have nice representation for all three. We got contributions from around the world, and again, we got contributions covering the full range of scales for the solar system, exoplanets, stars, galaxies, and the large structure of the universe. sillier decided to pass those off to do their work. The next step and this is to form the survey definition committees, and that we are going to be doing very soon in the next month to two months. I am going this for two reasons. First, you might want to know what they are doing in more detail, and we are hoping one of the things he will discuss is how you want to engage with this process. So I wanted you to have a better idea of what this process is going to look like. In order to produce the recommendations that these definition communities will send to the time allocation committee, there's going to be kind of three blocks of tasks. The first is these committees will have to organize themselves. We will ask those on the committees have not been intimately engaged with Roman before, the first task is going to be becoming familiar with the mission, the capabilities, the science requirements, and this existing community input that we have received as well as all of the work that has gone into helping to define and design Roman. In the community will need to discuss this prioritized science driver that has arisen from the community input and identify what additional input they think they need in order to do this. And also determine how they want to get additional input throughout the process. The next step, the next block of tasks, is to kind of workshop the ideas for this. To start looking at trade-off analyses for different observational strategies against the list of prioritized science drivers. What happens if we choose this suite of filters versus that? How does that affect the balance of science that the community surveys can do? And assess the feasibility's of the most promising strategies, and then narrow it down, iterate, refine, to the most promising strategies, perform detailed scheduling studies and depth estimates. In all of this, we expect the committee to be engaging with the community to be reaching out to experts reaching out and experts in stiffing science areas to be holding workshops or something -- things that allow people to come together and provide input. And then finally they were right up the recommendations for that

observation time allocation committee. And in addition to engaging with the community broadly will have funded science teams that can provide some support, and that is in terms of assessing different strategies and impact on science cases. We will have support from the same centers in the projects as well. And then, once a selection is made for the community survey program, what exactly it is going to be, these communities are going to have to tell the Saint centers how to implement the surveys to meet their vision. It also to produce a report that they can pass out to you as a community so you can understand what the surveys are going to be a what their capabilities are going to be. My, so, will be looking to those communities who will reflect the other science community wants to see those enabled science surveys, as well as a diversity of the community and will use allies romance data. And we want community members to have a significant scientific technical or community building expertise, and that is related to the work of finding these core service, who have a community oriented mind-set. People who can speak your community. So if you have any of these relevant expertise in their capacity to serve, I encourage you to consider self nominating. So, summarizing this, the final -- the second stage of the initial request for community input with this past Friday, the white papers we do, so those self nominations will be coming out soon, once the teams are announced as when we anticipate putting out the call for self nominations. They can see this upcoming call when it comes from our details of what we expect the task of these communities to be of the timeline in the support. It is going to be relatively light weight on the N. And that, look for additional opportunities of the neck one and a half years roughly to provide input to these community to these communities. So I can go through the rest of this fairly quickly as Julie mentioned it already. But working groups are going to be wrapping up, they are your opportunity to, if you really invested in a particular topic to add your voice to the conversation. And these are some examples of working groups that we have had in the past, and calibration software development that are currently active. We do expect the opportunity that Julie mentioned that will be coming again. To -- we anticipate a low offer an additional science investigation as well as support for working with the instrument team. The science collaborations will kick off and we hope they will be active over a long time. Back of the mission, and this is your opportunity to engage with Roman science. As a community independently of any peer review selections. And then, what we are used to doing. The general investigation opportunities where you put in proposals for funding and for FSOC observation. so I will finish on this final slide, which gives you a list of ways to keep up to date. Especially with Roman scientists. You can read it through here, it will be posted somewhere eventually to look at. But there are multiple forms for you are to stay up to date including approximately monthly community forms with project status updates and other presentations and also, you have representatives that you have a roaming Saints interest group within Pfizer's the science officer gutter and there is a Roman advisory committee that advises the STI director here. If you go to their dirt website you will find the people that are on them and I encourage you to reach out to them with thoughts because they are your representative to the project in the space telescope. In Anchorage it is to continue to look for this ongoing series. And with that I'll take any questions that anyone has.

Thank you, do you have any questions online? Okay we'll start with the questions than in the room. What is that noise? That is a question that's coming in I just have a quick question about the paper is expected to be posted on the archive for correlated and put together by you folks,

or is it up to the individuals to post them. We would not be putting them in archive, but we encourage people to do so. We do expect to make them publicly available for the community to read. Just one little note here, in the previous slide that said that the next solicitation was roses number 23 but it was actually 24. Oh, yes, I need to change that you so much. Are there the questions? the questions are there? Have a question since I'm next to the microphone, and it's a very general one, and that is, what keeps you up at night in terms of excitement about this process, and the fears of this process? I would say, the most challenging and also exciting thing is that we do have a compressed timeline right. This is -- we are looking to launch really around the corner right in terms of these things. And so, it will be -- I think it will be a challenge to do this on the timeline that we need to in order to meet what we want to provide to the community and what we have at the Saint center in order to prefer Provence. And I also think it's an opportunity because I think it will really -- we need to engage with people seriously and meaningfully and consistently to make this happen. And I think that would lead to really good conversations that otherwise could beat if flagged over time. So I think it's both a challenge and opportunity this this timeline. Yesterday and a half years is not as long as it used to be. I know all working diligently to make sure it does launch towards his commitment date, so people shouldn't expect this to drag on forever. Yes in the service do need to be defined quite earlier than that. Okay, then any of the in the room? So thank you very much its thinker again Thank you.

Linda Harris: Juneteenth Celebration, the History of Harriet Tubman, the Underground Railroad, and Emancipation in Maryland

We're running a few minutes late, but it can be worth going into the coffee break a little bit because the next presentation that we have, which isn't actually a top of really a presentation is going to be a very special one. And I have the honor to introduce Linda Harris was a director of program and events of the Harriet Tubman Museum and education center. So she is here and joined by David who is a composer and a musician and an instructor at the Duke Ellington school in Washington, D.C. and bassist extraordinaire Emory Diggs who was working his way up here. Watch out for the pace. Together they form the cold journey stories, and they were educators and inspire us with some songs and stories of Harriet Tubman to the underground railroad in recognition of Juneteenth, but we're hoping that everyone recognized it yesterday, we are doing it again here today.

Hello, everyone. I am absolutely honored to be here. As difficult as my husband. Emma retakes, and I am the director of programming at the Harriet Tubman Museum. His things that we did to get people interested in Harriet Tubman, and history, in the ancestors is that we got to the communities. I wasn't always interested in Harriet Tubman are in history, I majored in business in Maryland which they started a real estate business which they had for 33 years and they retired, but what changed me is the event of 2020, which I'm sure has changed many of us. It was devastating for many of us. And for me I felt that because we had the pandemic, I can see my family friends and I couldn't move about and I felt as if my freedom had been taken away. So I had to find what that meant. And my father, when I was ten years old, he gave me a book about Harriet Tubman. And I still have that book, was called runaway. And I read the book. And

after reading it, Harriet Tubman was born in 1822, just on the each to ensure and I've never been to before but I wrote a book on the first, then I watch the coverage of George Floyd. And how that absolutely frightened me. Frightened me as an African American in America. So I said you know what I have to do a Harriet Tubman did I have to go and figure out this other guy of railroad and what it was all about. So I drove to Cambridge, but an hour and a half, maybe about an hour and a half from here and I met with a bunch of historians and they talk to me about Harriet Tubman and give me a bunch of books. And I decided you know what -- I'm going to do what she did. I'm going to walk from the plantation where she was enslaved, to Philadelphia Pennsylvania where she met William still an abolitionist. So I trained through mid-September, the slides you will see myself and several other women, who embarked upon this journey along the Underground Railroad. When I finished that walk, a change me. I live in a bubble and I had a pretty good life, I was well educated, and you know I had a good education and good family. So I was in this book will really worrying about but if everyone else was worried about. In this bubble. And it became a moral imperative for me to begin to connect with my community. In a do it now through talking about Harriet Tubman talking about freedom. And when I got from that walk was freedom -- my definition is putting 1 foot in front of the other. Going towards a common positive course of community and we can be free because none of us are free until we are all free. So, we make it interesting, and everybody we know that music is a one medium that we can coalesce. Especially around, so what we do is to be sing. So, our first song is freedom, and it's a song that I wrote, and I was walking along the Underground Railroad. In any of my tambourine. All right. Getting your attention in case you cannot fall asleep on me.

♪♪ Freedom ♪♪ Everlasting, everyone. Daring ♪♪ Marching on ♪♪ We are walking ♪♪ With Harriet ♪♪ To freedom, to freedom ♪♪ We are walking ♪♪ With Harriet to freedom ♪♪ To freedom ♪♪ And when we step across the line, we are going to turn back and bring you along because we are walking with Harriet ♪♪ We are working with Harriet to freedom ♪♪ My sisters are walking ♪♪ My brothers are walking ♪♪ We are marching along ♪♪ And when we step across the line ♪♪ We started our movement ♪♪ Because freedom, freedom, belongs to us ♪♪ We can't stop ♪♪ Cannot stop ♪♪ We cannot stop ♪♪ No we can't stop ♪♪ We are on a mission we've got to sing our song ♪♪ And when we step across the line ♪♪ We are going to turn back and bring you along because we are walking with Harriet to freedom ♪♪ We are walking ♪♪ With Harriet to freedom ♪♪ To freedom ♪♪ We are walking, which carry it, to freedom, to freedom. And what we step across the line, we start a mighty movement ♪♪ Because freedom ♪♪ Freedom ♪♪ Belongs... Belongs... Belongs belongs -- it belongs ♪♪ It belongs to us ♪♪

So let's talk a minute about Harriet Tubman, she was an astronomer. She knew to follow Flores, the North Star. It she knew it late between -- you can correct me if I'm wrong, with the big dipper in the Little dipper meat, she was following the North Star, but before Harriet Tubman she was born here in 8022. in her ear Tubman her grandmother was brought here from the west coast of Africa. From Ghana. She is from the Asante tribe. and the SRT tribe had various religious beliefs. A Patheon of beliefs of God's and the land and the spirits saw her grandmother, modesty, she was an African who eventually captured and put on the spaceship, and travel from three to five months on the middle passage brought to the shores of Cambridge. In day

she was told an auction off into slavery. So if you can imagine what it would have been like to have been taken from your homeland, and put on a ownership entrapment for five months. On a ship like a book on a bookcase. tuning toward that journey and then coming to a man that you have in learning language that you cannot speak and people that you've never seen people do not look like you and you are expected to survive in that environment. So you essentially become a motherless child. So the rhythms in the Akkadians that the enslaved people use when they were put on the slave ships, they came from various parts of the West Coast of Africa and had different dialects but one thing that they knew that they knew the rhythms. Because they hugged them. City songs that we now know, that have been translated into English and put on charts, with notes and staves in bars and shovel cleft and bass clef, enslaved people did not know that. They had the rhythms and the beat of the drums. In the van chosen instrument that was brought to us from Africa. So, they communicated through code. Through these rhythms. This is one song that you may know that was a rhythm that they brought with them. But it was an expression of how they felt. Especially being taken away. That motherless child. [begins to hum]

♪ ♪ ♪ Sometimes ♪ ♪ I feel ♪ ♪ Like a motherless child ♪ ♪ Sometimes I feel like a motherless child ♪ ♪ Sometimes ♪ ♪ I she you ♪ ♪ Like a motherless child, a long way from home ♪ ♪ A long way from home ♪ ♪ Sometimes ♪ ♪ I feel ♪ ♪ Like I am almost done ♪ ♪ Sometimes ♪ ♪ I feel ♪ ♪ Like I am almost done ♪ ♪ Sometimes ♪ ♪ I feel ♪ ♪ Like I am almost done ♪ ♪ A long way from home, a long way from home ♪ ♪ ♪ ♪

As I said, Harriet Tubman was an astronomer and a naturalist. On the eastern shores, it was knitted D.C. area now, it was a big breeding ground for enslaved people. It was slavery in the far south and Maryland is right before below the Mason Dixon line, say of the union and the Confederacy, but waited made it different was that the enslaved people they were breeding them to sell themselves to see that massive cotton industry. So the industry for the enslavers and Marilyn were breeding, and tobacco and muskrat pallet. European roots loved muskrat pallet. And of course they are a the fourth thing the area and smelling the work. So the reason we know her well she didn't invent the Underground Railroad or what she defers a traveler, but we know her so well because she traveled 13 times. And as I told you I walked from the plantation Ferguson plantation to Philadelphia, they hundred and 50 miles. And I walked 20 miles a day -- and I didn't do the walk during the night and there were no dogs chasing me, on horseback, for the was difficult. It's something about walking or communing with nature looking up at the sky the current we are. And I think probably you understand that, in its teeth changed me. I'm sure a change Harriet, and Harriet knew that her first walk out in 1849, when she walked in the night in the winter when I walked with my group we had all the clear. We sat with consultants. And they told me he would choose Emmett Hanna back I needed and the kind of material I needed for the clothing I needed so it made the walk tolerable but it was still difficult. But imagine. The imagine the the enslaved people and the conditions and they made that decision to walk to freedom. With no shoes. With no shoes, backpacks, no place to get water. I cannot imagine. Because the work that I did 20 miles a day and many of you may be walkers and runners and bikers at that anything -- it was hard. He was very difficult. But I had the courage and the tenacity to do that. And you must think about that. Going up I'm old, I am a grandmother, but when I grew up in school, I was told that the enslaved people were not very

bright and not very strong or tough or had no purpose, but that was further from the truth. Harriet Tubman as I said, her followers were boatbuilders, the Europeans went to specific parts of Africa to find people that had a specific skills appended to what they needed to be done. So her father was a very smart man. She was a very smart woman she never meant to read or write of the King's English but she knew something more -- he had the emotional intelligence and a great desire. To leave something that was intolerable and walked to freedom and find her way. So, she followed -- the Underground Railroad was a system if you love the people, abolitionists, free African Americans, locations, safe houses, and journeys, each Jenny was a Kiley Bess thank journey that was well plotted out. And then they wrote code songs -- as I told you they came with different dialects but they use these rhythms to create the code songs. And so if they were working in the fields and singing oftentimes they would think they were just thinking and singing but they were actually plotting to find freedom. And so the drinking gourd is a song that we will do now, the drinking gourd is a shape of a constellation. The Big Dipper and the little dipper. And at the base of the West and North Star. There was that song follow the drinking gourd. And it was a song -- but all right get ready. Were getting ready to walk to freedom. I want you to listen to the words.

♪♪ Followed the drinking gourd ♪ ♪ Follow the drinking gourd. Before the old man is waiting to carry you to freedom. Follow the drinking gourd. While the river bank makes a mighty good road. And the trees will show you the way ♪ ♪ Left foot right foot traveling on ♪ ♪ Follow the drinking gourd. Come on and follow Judah drinking gourd. Follow the drinking gourd. Before the old man is waiting to secure you to freedom ♪ ♪ Follow the drinking gourd ♪ ♪ When the sun comes back, and the first quail calls ♪ ♪ Follow the drinking gourd ♪ ♪ For the old man is waiting just to carry you to freedom ♪ ♪ Follow the drinking gourd ♪ ♪ Well deliver lies between two hills, follow the drinking gourd ♪ ♪ There is another river on the other side ♪ ♪ Follow the drinking gourd ♪ ♪ Left foot tech foot traveling on ♪ ♪ Follow the drinking gourd ♪ ♪ For the old man is waiting just to carry you to freedom ♪ ♪ Follow the drinking gourd ♪♪

So that was telling people the enslaved people to go north. In the abolitionist the synthesizer that was going to help. Those code songs. Harriet Tubman, she was enslaved for 27 years. One of the Eastern shore, her first walk was in 1849. She walked 11 miles from George Custer County into Caroline County, and met with the young woman named Hannah who is one of the first safe houses. There are many, many safe houses along the route. The interesting thing on the east ensure is the African Americans they were enslaved but it was a large community of free African Americans and they were very helpful in this underground railroad and the success of it. So she gets to freedom, gets a Philadelphia, is there for about a year, less than a year maybe nine months, and she realizes that she was alone. In this freedom doesn't feel really good because I know that my family and my friends are back there. Sure she makes the trip 13 times, she walks this past 13 times which in and of itself is unbelievable. And by the third or fourth time, she had assistance, she used horses and carriages in both MS begat later on into the 1850s and trains. She was unselfish. he believed that she had to get her family out. So, she -- she believes in community and love. And what's on the playing? for plane fare well. So there's a book written by Kate Larson, she spent 20 years researching Harriet Tubman in her life -- and one Sunday we absolutely know that Harriet Tubman saying was that song called

farewell, I don't know if anyone saw the movie but they opened with that song. And again they had to talk in code, and it's astonishing to me how the enslavers never forget out these code songs. Absolutely underestimating the enslaved people. But when she was going her first timeout, she couldn't tell her mother -- her mother's name was -- and they believed in family. And her three older sisters Harriet's older sisters had been sold into slavery when she was a little girl. In one of the things that her mother feared was her children being sold off. so Harriet leaving, she can tell her mother. She sang in college. And she sang her song to let her know that I'm leaving and I will come back and get you.

♪♪ I'm sorry I have to leave you ♪ ♪ Oh farewell, farewell ♪ ♪ But I will meet you in the morning ♪ ♪ Oh farewell ♪ ♪ Farewell ♪ ♪ I am sorry ♪ ♪ I must leave you ♪ ♪ Farewell ♪ ♪ Farewell ♪ ♪ But I will meet you in the morning ♪ ♪ Oh farewell ♪ ♪ Farewell ♪ ♪ I am going to freedom ♪ ♪ Heading for the promised land ♪ ♪ But I will meet you in the morning ♪ ♪ Farewell oh farewell ♪ ♪ I'm sorry I have to leave you ♪ ♪ But I am coming back real soon ♪ ♪ I am going to the promised land ♪ ♪ Oh farewell ♪ ♪ Farewell ♪ ♪ ♪

She makes these 13 walks in the kind that's fine walk she anyone. She is a naturalist because she knows how to use the sounds of the animals in the words in the indigenous bird are our on the eastern shores the barred owl, and Harriet Tubman and she was coming to get people -- they have the round of viewpoints, they use the sound of the barn owl -- Windows within a walk with her they knew it was time to get ready to go. Again how the enslavers -- how they could not figure this out astonishes me. Because she knew if it was a dark night or a cloudy night and you couldn't see the stars receive a Northstar she knew that if the moss was going on the right side of the tree that she was going the right way. When she carried babies with her she was able to take the herbs and make a sedative to keep the baby's quiet. So that's pretty ingenious stuff. So an astronomer following the sky international is making use of the sky. She made these 13 trips, and in 1857 I was her last trip. She got off her friends and family to freedom. And then what happens? The civil war breaks out, 1861. Abraham Lincoln was president of the time as we now know, he was so impressed with Harriet's governments that he asks her to go to South Carolina, and she had not to freedom, she was a free woman, she said I had heard about you, you are a spy you can leave cc do not get caught, and we need you in the Civil War. denial is not a font for the country than I had enslaved me but she did, she was 5-foot to the survey centered off the South Carolina she's the only woman to fight in the Civil War. She goes there, and she fights in the River raid. She's put on a boat, and she goes and she takes out the Confederate ships and wins that battle. The only woman who did. Stays in South Carolina for three years, and she starts she might be considered the only person to know as a food truck -- she was down there selling sandwiches and cookies to raise money for their newly enslaved freedom women to help them get acclimated to living free. Before the Civil War, Jon Brown, Jon Brown -- she and Frederick Douglass, she informed this secret group called the secret six. And they help fight in the raid on Harpers Ferry, she was supposed to go to Harpers Ferry and help them with the that she got sick. And we know what happened to Jon Brown. After the war was over, she worked with Susan B. Anthony. Susan B. Anthony, there is this movement the women's suffrage movement. In Susan B. Anthony was so impressed with Harriet Tubman, for her ability to lead people that she hired her to give speeches. So she go around the country, giving speeches

about women's movement, about rights, not so much for women, but she believes that everyone should have rights, and African Americans and Heather, so she went around giving speeches, she was much around in 1937... And if Anthony if you ever read about it and she credits Harriet Tubman is helping the suffrage movement. In woman get the right to vote 1920. And she dies in 1930. But she is Hertha so it facilities someone was very important to the movement. After she gets settled in what happens? I have to go back -- 1850s an important year, 1850, the fugitive act was passed and the reason why the movement on the Underground Railroad really increases is because the act says that any African American captain then enslaved or not could be captured and sold down south. They needed to feed that massive and lucrative cotton industry which is the fourth largest industry in the country at the time and made people and seeing the wealthy on of free labor. So Harriet Tubman had to get to Canada and she got lots and lots of people to Canada and she did that until there is a huge settlement of African Americans in Canada. She also never went below South Carolina. That helped orchestrate the movement to Mexico, those are very sick sophisticated route between abolitionists on the upper down the road on the East Coast. So? What is our next song -- so when I think about shoes, probably have a hundred pairs of shoes. Excessive is what we've become. The enslaved people risk everything, they didn't have shoes -- and I walked in the Eastern shore ground, and there is rocks and their prickly little things. There are all over the place and there is a course tree to use to make votes so they had to walk along those roads and they were stepping on this kind of thing. But they didn't care because it meant getting to freedom. So another coat song was I have shoes. In the song says I have shoes and you've got shoes and that all people issues are getting to heaven and that met the enslavers they believed in God but that they really did they believe in God when they were enslaving other human beings? They were singing beside the sounds in the field and they were getting ready to go. Saint I got shoes.

♪♪ I've got shoes you've got shoes ♪♪ All got sufficient children have shoes ♪♪ Kevin ♪♪ Kevin ♪♪ Everybody talking about heaven ♪♪ Has ended ♪♪ I'm gonna walk all over God's heaven ♪♪ I have wings ♪♪ You have wings ♪♪ All God's children have wings ♪♪ Has been ♪♪ Heaven ♪♪ Everybody talking about heaven ♪♪ Has ended ♪♪ F I've got crowns and you've got crowns ♪♪ All of God children Crohn's ♪♪ And when I get to heaven than a put on my crown all over God's heaven ♪♪ Heaven ♪♪ Everybody talking about heaven ♪♪ I'm gonna walk all over God's heaven ♪♪ All right -- we can elect the guys walk ♪♪ ♪♪

Here he is on the base of the banjo, and you're feeling good because you're walking and beaten the heck out of being enslaved. And once you cross over if he good. You are running -- I remember when I got to Kennett Square right on the line between Delaware and I had a lot of extra energy and I don't know where it was coming is probably delirious, but I am so excited. So imagine how they felt. And then how they felt. Yes. The baseline the sound from Africa. All right.

♪♪ ♪♪ You just feeling so good aren't you don't you feel good? Oh you've got a harp, I have a heart ♪♪ All got children has a heart ♪♪ When I get to heaven I'm going to play over God's heaven ♪♪ Hedging, everyone talking about heaven ♪♪ I'm gonna play all over God's heaven ♪♪ I have shoes ♪♪ You've got shoes ♪♪ Was in a put on her shoes ♪♪ Gonna walk ♪♪ Within a scene ♪♪ And you can a shout ♪♪ And were gonna walk around all over God's

heaven 🎵 🎵 Walker Little for God's heaven 🎵 🎵 And walk all over God's heaven 🎵 🎵 I've got shoes 🎵 🎵 You've got shoes 🎵 🎵 And with all issues we are going to walk all over the cut has been walking 🎵 🎵 We are free. 🎵 🎵

So now let us talk about Juneteenth. We celebrated and now it is a national holiday. And we like holidays. A number retired now so it is a holiday. But we get the day off. An anxious point you to reflect to the extent that you can. About what that really means. So the emancipation proclamation ISA get too tired saying that when I was a kid, but Abraham Lincoln signed, and said okay were were going to free the enslaved people. We cannot take them out of bondage. I'm looking to consider than human beings. For can I consider them Americans. 1857 -- they have the Dred Scott case, and the decision was that African Americans were not Americans. He would not have the rights -- they were just hypocrisy. So we had the Civil War so drink and sciences in 1863, Abraham Lincoln, but not too many states know that they are free -- can you imagine not having a document being signed in 1863, and you do not know it. Now in Texas, they were the last state to have the enslaved people being free, Texas in 1865, even in the state of Maryland she helped fight in the Civil War, and help Abraham Lincoln -- she was very mad at him by the way, if you have any interest in reading that timeline she goes to Lincoln and says how could you do such a thing? How could you sign a document in 1863 and I did not know that not it in the state of Maryland until 1864? How could that be? Texas being the last state to be freed. In Texas is still having those problems. I'm telling you Texas looks like -- I don't want to talk politics but I am talking politics because they can try to get back to where they were. So as we have these holidays, Juneteenth and Martin Luther King, they are real. My ancestors making sacrifices for the development of this country. In fact everything that you see in here it really is a product of who we are. It is in our bloodline, redone some amazing things and we deserve the rights. We deserve freedom we deserve to be treated fairly. And I cannot say that enough, Salome had these holidays not considered just a day off to take a walk on the particle have lunch with your friends over for up to what really happened and what it really means and why it is important to keep fees dates in our minds and practice community and practice love. And one thing that I think Harriet Tubman really espoused if you will is that if you love yourself as a human being, keep the love of your people. So another song, this is not necessarily a coat song but it's one that I've adopted in my opinion. And it really is the epitome of what it was like to be an enslaved person and then help others along upon this community and still move forward to have rights and be treated fairly and kindly. What are you playing there? All aboard! While he is going to get on board. But that's not the song I was thinking about, but we will do that one. But another one is get on board, so we know that growing up I can't affect the underground rollovers was an actual train -- but when I was walking from the Dorchester and to Caroline County, there's this train track, so I decided I was gonna get off the road and go down the train track, and a kind of felt like I was a train moving on the Underground Railroad. In this song also became a civil rights song. Get on board this train, it is moving and moving to freedom. All right are you ready?

🎵 🎵 Get on board 🎵 🎵 Children get on board 🎵 🎵 Little children get on board 🎵 🎵 Little children get on board there is room for many more 🎵 🎵 Get on board little children 🎵 🎵 Get on board little children 🎵 🎵 There is room for many and more 🎵 🎵 I see the train 🎵 🎵 Is coming around

the curve 🎵 🎵 And get on board little children 🎵 🎵 get on board little children 🎵 🎵 Get on board little children 🎵 🎵 There is room for many or more. Get on board little children 🎵 🎵 Get on board little children 🎵 🎵 Get on board little children is room for many or more 🎵 🎵 I see the train it's coming 🎵 🎵 She's coming around the curve 🎵 🎵 She's using her Steve and is exciting every nerve 🎵 🎵 Get on board little children 🎵 🎵 There is room for many or more 🎵 🎵 Get him toward little children 🎵 🎵 Get on board little children 🎵 🎵 Get on board little children 🎵 🎵 Is room for many or more 🎵 🎵

So that is a metaphor -- get on board. Thank you all so much. Now this train we are going north because Nork seems to be the place since to be the progressive place to be for freedom and for equal rights and free education. That's what we want. We all want the same things. So I pretty much told you about Harry to Ms. Like she was a naturalist and astronomer and she believed in community. She believed her family. She made to sacrifices 13 times to help family and friends find freedom. So, I've adopted this motto -- and I invite you to come to our museum we are on the Eastern shore when you come there we are a small museum, nonprofit, but what I like to do is I take you on the Underground Railroad, we can walk any miles you want from two to five to 500 miles -- if you want to calm down enough to spend the week planned gonna walk the Underground Railroad because what it did for me is that a change my life. I change my perspective on life and things. You see people differently. I see them differently because I love myself so much and I can extend love to everyone else. Unless you mess with me if you mess with me that something different. From a heart was opened and I didn't have that before and I let this little all I cared about is what I was doing and what my two kids were doing and nothing has really mattered but we cannot live in a bubble we have to come out of that bubble and extend our love in our care for everyone else. within a wade into the water now. Another coat song. These guys are scripts but I'm going to go with them. Late in the water is another coat song wade in the water -- when they were going down into her being chased and pursued by dogs and then on horseback and they would go into the water. And what the Watergate -- this moving water would mask their small for the dogs could not up the scent. They would wait in the water. A song that we know but it is a rhythm and a cadence for the enslaved people that they brought with them all right -- we wade the water.

🎵 🎵 Wade in the water 🎵 🎵 Wade in the water 🎵 🎵 Children, wade in the water 🎵 🎵 God is going to travel the waters 🎵 🎵 Wade in the water 🎵 🎵 Wade in the waters 🎵 🎵 Children, weight wade in the water 🎵 🎵 God is going to trouble the waters 🎵 🎵 Who was that there are Justin White? 🎵 🎵 God is going to trouble the waters 🎵 🎵 Must be the band of the Israelites 🎵 🎵 God is going to trouble the waters 🎵 🎵 Come in wade in the waters 🎵 🎵 Wade in the waters 🎵 🎵 Children wade in the waters 🎵 🎵 God explained to trouble trouble the waters 🎵 🎵 Who is that all Justin White 🎵 🎵 God is going to trouble the waters 🎵 🎵 Must be the day and that Moses led. 🎵 🎵 God is going to trouble the waters 🎵 🎵 Come and wait in the water 🎵 🎵 Wade in the water children wade in the water 🎵 🎵 God is going to trouble the waters 🎵 🎵 God is going to trouble the waters 🎵 🎵 God is going to trouble the waters 🎵 🎵 🎵 🎵

Status and get you going -- thank you. [Applause] Is putting one step in front of the other that's what the Underground Railroad is. I don't know if I said this earlier, but I coined this motto. Fun

to hear it in you. One aspect of what she did in and place it will change you your community. It changes how you see things and how you feel. And how it helps to be progressive and productive. Because it did that for me. And that's what Harriet did. She became a productive human being and freed her people and that is what we want. Our. All right thank you. David loves to play. And we left the scene. But I want to leave you with love and what that means. Love will guide us. Peace will guide us. And I have learned to love myself so much that things that people say about me just roll off my back because I know I have a larger purpose. And if I love myself and I can love anyone. I have a granddaughter, she tells me she calls me Nana mommy, and she said your extra walk each of the eight normal grandma mommy she was sitting here should be counted in her seat covering her face because she sail caught this woman is crazy.

But love will guide us 🎵 🎵 Piece has tried us 🎵 🎵 The whole inside of us will lead us on our way
🎵 🎵 On the road from 🎵 🎵 Love will guide us, through the hardened night, if you cannot 🎵 🎵
Speak like an angel if you cannot 🎵 🎵 Speak for 4,000, then you can give from deep in you 🎵 🎵
You can chase the world, with your love 🎵 🎵 I said you love will guide guide us 🎵 🎵 Piece has
tried us 🎵 🎵 The hope inside of us 🎵 🎵 Will lead the way 🎵 🎵 Love will guide us 🎵 🎵 Hope will
lead us 🎵 🎵 level guide us 🎵 🎵 Through the hardened night so travel the Underground Railroad,
and nine, and you will find the answers. Thank you so much. [Applause] 🎵 Through the
hardened night [Applause]

Thank you so much for that informative and of course entertaining presentation for all of us. We really appreciate that. So at this point within a going to a break. For gonna come back in about -- will come back on time at 3:30 when we will see you often thank you.

Live captioning was provided by CaptionMax. Some formatting and light editing was included by the Local Organizing Committee for added clarity, but there was no attempt to correct all live captioning errors.

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